

**MEDICAL REHABILITATION MODERN PARADIGMS
AND STRATEGIC SIGNIFICANCE OF FUNCTIONAL
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E-mail: biologiya203@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18821348>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th February 2026Accepted: 27th February 2026Online: 28th February 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

This scientific thesis analyzes complex measures aimed at restoring impaired functions of the human body. The study classifies specialized areas of rehabilitation and scientifically substantiates the role of this field in modern medicine in improving the quality of life after pathological conditions.

Introduction

In recent years, medical rehabilitation has emerged as an independent and strategically important area of the healthcare system, and the volume of scientific research focused on functional recovery is expanding significantly. The concepts developed by foreign researchers have made it possible to interpret rehabilitation not only as a post-treatment stage, but as a continuous, complex and evidence-based process that begins with the acute stage of the disease.

In this area, Howard A. Rusk substantiated the principles of early and continuous rehabilitation, and the clinical effectiveness of a multidisciplinary approach was scientifically proven. Sir Ludwig Guttmann's studies showed the positive effect of active rehabilitation and sports therapy on functional and social recovery after spinal cord injuries. In the field of neurorehabilitation, Edward Taub developed.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, scientific and practical research is also being conducted systematically in the field of medical rehabilitation. In particular, specialists from the Tashkent Medical Academy and the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Rehabilitation have developed phased rehabilitation programs after neurological, traumatological and cardiological diseases. These studies have achieved an increase in the rate of patients' return to work and social activities by assessing the functional state, drawing up individual rehabilitation plans and using complex physiotherapeutic methods.

Conceptual foundations of rehabilitation

Medical rehabilitation is a dynamic system aimed at maximally compensating for biopsychosocial opportunities limited as a result of pathological processes or traumatic injuries. In the modern healthcare strategy, rehabilitation is considered not just an additional

procedure, but an integral and final stage of the treatment cycle. Its fundamental essence is to turn the patient into an active member of society.

Basic principles of rehabilitation

Effective rehabilitation must be based on the following principles:

Early start: Rehabilitation should begin in the intensive care unit of the hospital.

Continuity and continuity: The recovery process should seamlessly transition from the hospital to the home environment.

Individuality: Creating a plan based on the reserve capabilities of each patient.

Multidisciplinary: The process involves a team of doctors, physiotherapists, psychologists, speech therapists and occupational therapists.

Reasons for the relevance of the field today:

Demographic aging and chronic pathologies: The aging trend among the world's population has increased the need for geriatric rehabilitation several times.

The "reverse side" of high-tech medicine: As a result of medical developments, the survival rate of patients with severe injuries who were previously doomed to death has increased, but this has led to their need for long-term professional care.

Integration of digital technologies: The use of robotic mechanotherapy and biological feedback systems is giving results 3-4 times more effective than traditional methods.

Conclusion

Medical rehabilitation is one of the priority areas of the modern healthcare system and is a complex scientific and practical process aimed at reducing functional impairments after diseases and injuries and improving the quality of life. Studies confirm that starting rehabilitation measures at an early stage significantly increases functional restoration indicators, reduces the level of disability, and improves the clinical prognosis. Rehabilitation programs based on a multidisciplinary approach allow for an integrative assessment of the patient's somatic, psychological, and social state. Methods based on neuroplasticity mechanisms activate the compensatory capabilities of the central nervous system and ensure the restoration of motor and cognitive functions.

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